

“Peaceful co-existence in the society: A study of the *The Day Blinked and The Death Certificate* by Alobwed’Epie.”

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Abstract

The notion of peaceful co-existence goes along with interacting and otherness. In intercultural communication, self-retreat has often been considered as a solution to living together in the society. This article examines the construction of living together in *The Day Blinked* and *The Death Certificate* by Alobwed’Epie.” through the interactions amongst characters in the novels under review. Material were collected from the reading of Alobwed’Epie’s *The Death Certificate* and *The Day God Blinked*. theoretical and critical works, books and scientific articles. These literary works contribute to the notion that Literature shapes the society for the betterment of everyone thereby leading us to use the cosmopolitan theory by Kwame Anthony Appiah which advocates for solidarity, mutual respect and dialogue across boundaries amongst citizens in the society. The theory is equally out to promote living together by advocating the non practice of tribalism and marginalisation in the society. After reading our corpuses, we came to the following conclusions : that there is soildarity and generosity amongst Ewawains, Joseph gives employment to Lucia Ntang without practising tribalism, Joseph is promoting living together in example of Maria’s boyfriend attends even to patients without consultation fee nor money to carry on the tests, Minister of Social Affairs gives money to Lucia Ntang and her fatherless son, Mula offers him quality wine to Mongo Meka in France despite the fact that Mongo Meka has stolen public funds worth hundreds of millions in Ewawa. Furthermore, Mula offers both food and a drink to a man from Ndotelle who has come to Dande due to the death of Mongo Meka, the friends of Mula organise a party for him at their own expense where they eat and chat together, while Mula on his part, shows both solidarity, kindness and generosity towards Sonia by securing a post graduates studies in a Biberian university, the mother of Mengue Brigitte accomodates Lucia Ntang with her pregnancy despite the fact that Lucia Ntang is not from the same with her. Moreover, living together is practised in Ewawa by Jacqueline Diwona who maintains all the formal servants of Antoinette Yvonne without taking into consideration that some of them like Marie –Claire are not from her tribe.Lastly, Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese expresses generosity towards Lucia Ntang by giving her a lift from the British Council to Obele.

Keywords- Peaceful co-existence, society, dialogue, marginalisation, dominant groups.

Introduction

This paper examines how living together leads to feelings of belonging in both *The Day Blinked* and *The Death Certificate* by Alobwed’Epie. The cosmopolitan theory stpulates

that, humanbeings belong to the same society irrespective of their ethnic background, race, religion or cultural background. Futhermore, in a cosmopolitan community, differences between nations, religion, ethnic and cultural backgrounds are not taken into consideration because everybody in the society is considered as a brother or sister thus the promotion of peaceful coexistence. According to Thomas Pogge¹ cosmopolitanism is an inclusive normative theory that denotes a way of thinking in which all human beings are considered to belong to a single human community. Thus the focus of this approach as far as our article is concerned, is to encourage solidarity, unity, peace, love, mutual cooperation and tolerance without taking into consideration the tribe, the ruling class or the lower class. In sum, emphasis is on the cordial relation that exist between the ruling class and the governed indicates that the concept of 'self and others' has been relegated to the background in Ewawa thereby leading us to assert that, home is a place where one feels secured, belonging, relaxed, happy and is comfortable in the country.

Peaceful co-existence deals with the harmony that exist in the community between the ruling class and the non-ruling, a society in which the inhabitants do not discriminate in spite of the fact that they come from different tribal backgrounds in times of distress, employment and social gatherings. A society where both spatial and society marginality are absent. A society where in which persons from different tribes do not only accommodate others but equally feed the needy without taking into consideration of their ethnic backgrounds. A community where the poor are consulted in the hospital without bribing. A society where people from different ethnic groups buy food and drinks for others irrespective of the fact that they are not from the same tribe. The above picture is literary painted in both *The Day Blinked* and *The Death Certificate* by Alobwed'Epie through the experiences of the various characters in the both corpora.

The theoretical framework.

The cosmopolitan theory as opined by Kwame Anthony Appiah will be used in the writing of this article. His theory promotes solidarity, mutual respect and dialogue across boundaries amongst inhabitants in the society. The theory is also out to encourage living together by advocating for the non practice of ethnocentrism and marginalisation in the community. To Kwame Anthony², he on conversation across difference stated that dialogue

¹ Thomas Pogge. (1994). *Cosmopolitanism and Sovereignty*. Chris Brown.(Ed).*Political Resctructuring in Europe* :Ethical Perspectives. London :Routledge

² Kwame Anthony. (2006). *Cosmopolitan : Etics in a World of Strangers*. New York : W.W Norton

is the best path for mutual understanding in order to build a peaceful society. Furthermore, the author opined that humanity should transcend national ethnic, or ideological divisions so as to embrace the respect of universal human rights. Moreover, on moral obligation beyond borders, Kwame Anthony Appiah prescribed that human beings should show solidarity amongst one another in the society. Still on the theory of cosmopolitan theory of Kwame Anthony concerning peaceful co-existence in the community, Mohammad Hossein Seifkar³ in reviewing the work of Kwame Anthony mentioned above, observed that Kwame Anthony professed that the population should take interest in the lives of others, show kindness and generosity towards one another in the society. In addition, Mohammad Hossein Seifkar equally remarked that Kwame Anthony prescribed that people should practise eating, laughing, buying, attending parties and funerals together.

Additionally, on the cosmopolitan theory, Johan Galtung⁴ spelled out that the principles of social justice of respecting equal rights and equal opportunities should be respected by all the groups in the society. Moreover he also stated that ethnocentrism should be avoided by all in the society in order to have a harmonious country.

The first case of living together that we will mention in our article is that of that of a Passer-by Lady. The text tells us a lady meets someone bleeding on the road and carries the person to the hospital as the citation below attests:

According to the police evidence, she was caught helping a shot and badly wounded armed robber to escape police arrest. She did not deny the charge but said that when she was returning from Tuada International Airport at night, she met a badly wounded person (a human being) by the road side a few kilometres from Dande. He had bled so badly that he was slipping into a coma. So with the aid of some passengers from another vehicle she managed to put him in her car and drove him to the hospital.(The Day: 38).

From the above quotation, we would assume that the author is out to portray the woman as a kind person who helps people irrespective of their tribes as the narrator of the text tells us the lady meets a person bleeding and since the woman is afraid that the said person may die, with the help of other occupants from a different car, decides to carry the bleeding person to the hospital. We will then summarise our assessment on the above citation by affirming that, the novelist is out to show that the lady in question is promoting living together

³ Mohammad Hossein Schifkar. *An African Journal of Philosophy*. XXI, 2008 :303-314.

⁴ Johan Galtung. *Peace by Peaceful Means*. (1996). London :Sage Publications.

in the sense that, she takes care of another fellow man without asking where the man in distress comes from. Furthermore, the writer is indirectly calling all the Ewawains to emulate the example of the lady so that the Ewawa will be a serene one as far as tribalism is concerned. Thus the author is in favour of peaceful co-existence in Ewawa. Therefore leading us to apply the cosmopolitan theory as stipulated by Kwame Anthony Appiah⁵ where he prescribed firstly that, human beings should show solidarity amongst one another in the society and secondly that, the population should take interest in the lives of others, show kindness and generosity towards one another in the society. The pertinence of this theory in relation to our article is that, from the reaction of the passer-by lady and those other Ewawains from another car to help the helpless Ewawain, is to show that there is solidarity amongst Ewawains, there is generosity amongst Ewawains because the novelist tells us that the passer-by lady carries the bleeding person to the hospital at her own expense for fear that the man will die. The act of the passer-by Lady equally expresses charity and the concern for the welfare of another fellow Ewawain thereby pushing us to cite Ramose M.B⁶ Who stated that, expressing charity showing concern for the wellbeing of another in the society are signs that that particular community is living in peace. We will then conclude that there is the practice of living together in Ewawa as depicted in the action of both the Passer by Lady and those from a passing vehicle for they are out to save the life of a fellow human being, express solidarity, generosity towards another person.

Still on good samaritanism, our second example can be illustrated where the novelist tells us Joseph offers Lucia Ntang a job in a hotel not considering her tribe as seen in the citation below:

On the fifth day, I decided to go and see Joseph, the SG. I wanted him help me have a cleaning job in the Ministry to enable me save some money for the oncoming examinations. He received me well but thought a cleaning job in the Ministry for a graduate was degrading. So he said he would send me to one of the State hotels to supervise the cleaners. On my return, he gave me a ten thousand francs note, still with no strings attached. I thanked him. The salary was pretty good. I could save at least fifty thousand francs a month. (The Day: 69).

To appraise Lucia Ntang's words above, we would guess that the author is out to show that Joseph who is Secretary General in the Ministry of Territorial Administration is fighting

⁵ Kwame Anthony Appiah. (ibid).

⁶ Ramose M.B (1999). *African Philosophy through Ubuntu*. Harare : Mond Books.

clannism. The narrator tells us Joseph is from the ruling class but contrary to what other dignitaries of the ruling class do which is, employing only people from their tribe, Joseph has employed Lucia Ntang who is not from the ruling tribes. Lucia Ntang herself tells us that Joseph has given money to her without any hidden agenda. We will then end with this point by stating that, Joseph is a good man who offers employment to people in the community as seen in the case of Lucia Ntang without taking into consideration the person's tribe. Moreover, by affirming that, the novelist is indirectly calling on the people from the First and Second provinces who employ but girls and boys from their tribes as depicted in the novel to copy the example of Joseph thereby leading to the employment of Ewawains from other provinces which in turn will limit inter-ethnic conflict which is rife in Ewawa thereby leading us to apply the cosmopolitan theory of both Kwame Anthony Appiah and Johan Galtung. For Kwame Anthony Appiah⁷ and Johan Galtung⁸ are advocates for the non practice of ethnocentrism and marginalisation. The relevance of this approach to our article is that, the novelist tells us that Joseph employs Lucia Ntang without taking into consideration that she is from one of the marginised tribes in Ewawa for the text informs us that only persons from the ruling tribes are either recruited or employed in Ewawa. Thus by recruiting Lucia Ntang to work in the hotel, Joseph is practising peaceful co-existence therefore reducing the level of not only unemployment, but equally the level of animosity because the novelist informs us that the Ewawains from the 8th,9th and 10th provinces detests those from the ruling class in Ewawa because the ruling class employs or recruit those from their tribes.

The recruitment of Lucia Ntang by Joseph to work in a government hotel is also to express love and oneness in Ewawa thus leading us to quote Jude Asike⁹ who stated that, for people to live peacefully in any society, they have to express love to one another and connecting the citation to our research, we will assert that it is because of the love that Joseph has for Lucia Ntang that he decides to have her recruited to work in a government hotel to supervise all the cleaners in the hotel. Thus there is living together in Ewawa as seen in the act of Joseph towards Lucia Ntang. Still on the recruitment of Lucia Ntang by Joseph to work in the hotel, we will also apply the cosmopolitan theory of Johan Galtung¹⁰ who promoted social justice of respecting equal rights and equal opportunities for all the groups in the

⁷ Kwame Anthony Appiah. (ibid).

⁸ Johan Galtung. (ibid).

⁹ Jude Asike « The philosophical concept of 'ubuntu' as dialogic ethnic and transformation of political community in Africa » *New Journal of African Studies*. 12(1), July 2016 :1

¹⁰ Johan Galtung. (ibid).

society. Connecting this theory to our work, we will assert that, as seen in the text, Joseph is out to encourage living together in Ewawa by recruiting Lucia Ntang thus he implements the respect of equal rights and opportunities to all the Ewawains in the domain of recruitment for Lucia Ntang is recruited to work in the hotel irrespective of the fact that she comes from the marginalised tribe in Ewawa. We will then conclude that by giving employment to Lucia Ntang without discrimination, Joseph is promoting living together in Ewawa thereby reducing the number of persons who hate the ruling class for being the cause of unemployment in Ewawa.

Additionally, on how peaceful co-existence is promoted in the community by some men of good will as described in our novels, we will examine our third case by referring to the activities of Maria's lover. The narrator tells us in the novel that the boyfriend of Maria conducts a pregnancy test to Lucia Ntang without charging her a diam as the quotation that follows attests:

I decided to see a friend very versed in love making but who never got herself messed up as I thought I was. I told her my plight and she suggested I see a doctor immediately. I had to be examined and if it were positive, the age determined, prompt and necessary action would be taken. My heart took a jolt and almost stopped idiot. It can't be positive. Was God? Did the Holy Spirit visit me instead of my mother? She was called Maria I was called Lucy. Nonsense, but I had to see the doctor. See him with what? I had no money doctors wanted patients with hard cash and not those who came telling sad stories. I told my friend I had no money. She suggested we go see her boyfriend- a final year medical student who would be more understanding. We saw him. He examined me for free. He said there were signs of a three months eh,eh,e(The Day: 75).

In our commentaries concerning the above mentioned citation, we would presume that the novelist is showing that Maria's friend is not corrupt for he attends to Lucia Ntang despite the fact that she does not have money to do her pregnancy test unlike his colleagues who attend only to patients who give them money as the author presents in the novel. We will then summarise our observations on the excerpt by ascertaining that, the author is calling on those public medics who attend only to patients who give them money before consultation, to imitate the example of Maria's boyfriend who attends even to patients with neither the consultation fee nor money to carry on the test. Thereby leading us to say that the author is in

the same line of thought with both Chukwuebuka Gabriel O and Chioma Winifred Ezeanya¹¹ who commented that, in a society where there is harmony, citizens demonstrate solidarity mostly in times of difficulties. Relating the citation to our article, we will affirm that, Maria's boyfriend helps Lucia Ntang who wants to do a pregnancy test but has no money for both the consultation and the test. The fact that she is consulted and the pregnancy test done for free, is a glaring evidence to prove that Ewawains express solidarity to one another in times of distress as demonstrated by Maria's boyfriend. Furthermore, by asserting that, the writer is indirectly saying that the country needs but medical officers like that of Maria's boyfriend in order not only to promote living together in Ewawa therefore pushing us to use cosmopolitan theory of Johan Galtung¹² who promoted social justice of respecting equal rights and equal opportunities for all the groups in the society. Linking this approach to our research, we will affirm that the boyfriend of Maria is encouraging social justice in Ewawa because he consults both the rich and the poor unlike his colleagues who attend only to those who give them money. This act of Maria's boyfriend to Lucia Ntang goes a long way to ease the tension between the ruling class and the marginalised tribes in Ewawa thereby promoting living together in the society.

Moreover, on the role played by charitable people in the society to promote peaceful co-existence in Ewawa, we shall examine our fourth instance by citing the activities of the Minister of Social Affairs. Lucia Ntang tells us the Minister of Social Affairs gives her the sum of fifteen thousand (15,000) Frs. from her pocket as the excerpt below justifies:

Two weeks later the Minister invited me. She told me that they had just been split into the Ministry of Social Affairs and that of Women's Affairs. They therefore needed re-organisation in order to attribute powers to the different Directorates. She advised me to be patient. She gave me from her pocket, 15,000 Frs.

(The Day: 81).

From the above mentioned extract, we would suppose that the writer is pointing out that the Minister of Social Affairs is against tribalism for she gives money to Lucia Ntang to take care of her fatherless son without taking into consideration Lucia Ntang's tribe. This is contrary to what is illustrated in the novel where the people in power give favours only to graduates from their ethnic groups. We shall thus conclude that the author is calling on the

¹¹ Chukwuebuka Gabriel O and Chioma Winifred Ezeanya (2025). *Ubuntu Philosophy and the dialogue of Pan Africanism*. Nsuka: University of Nsuka

¹² Johan Galtung. (ibid).

governing class in Ewawa to copy the example of the Minister of Social Affairs so as to reduce or deal away with partiality in the community thereby leading us to apply the cosmopolitan theory of Johan Galtung¹³ where he stated that ethnocentrism should be avoided by all in the society in order to have a harmonious country. Connecting his theory to our research, we will establish that, the Minister of Social Affairs is practising living together because she is not tribalistic for in giving money to Lucia Ntang, the Minister does not take into consideration of Lucia Ntang unlike her fellow members of government who give favours only to persons who come from the dominant tribes in Ewawa as the novelist informs us in his novel. Furthermore, the act of the Minister will in turn lead to a reduction of hatred between people from the governing class and those from other provinces which is not hidden in Ewawa as illustrated in the novel. The novelist is once more considered as a campaigner of living together.

Still on the activities carried out by kind hearted people in the public to promote living together in Ewawa, the fifth illustration can be seen where the novel informs us that Mula offers a drink to Mongo Meka in a restaurant in France as the quotation that follows justifies:

He seemed to enjoy his meal without wine. I sipped mine to remind him. He got the message but did not react. That signaled something in me. I called the waiter and told him to bring a bottle of Medoc Superieur. He brought it and placed it in front of me. I gestured that it was for Monsieur Mongo Meka had a morsel in the mouth. He nodded in appreciation then swallowed noisily. His Adam's apple shuttled up and down as he said Merci. He gulped the first glass and belched in the manner of a palm wine drinker. (The Dead: 250).

Similarly, on the part played by people of good will to demonstrate peaceful co-existence in the community, the sixth example is when the writer informs us Mula feeds a villager from Ndotelle as Ndjock tells us in the excerpt that follows:

Mula offered him a bottle of low grade perhaps experimental red wine called bellevie. He got with a bow then gazed upward as if to thank God for the offer. He trained his eyes on Mula to decipher if he had seen him before. There was no inkling. As if to fight against Mula discovering his mistake and seizing back the wine, he tore open the red seal and in a single gulp, half the bottle went. Mula, Musa called. You are going to kill that fellow. He is drinking in an empty stomach

¹³ Johan Galtung. (ibid).

Mula plied into his pocket for money. He got 150 Frs. and asked the bar-man pain chargé. He got the bread with a double bow, made the sign of the cross and started chewing. (The Dead: 34-35).

To analyse the afore mentioned two citations, we would infer that Mula is not in favour of bias in Ewawa as the novel tells us that Mula offers good quality wine to Mongo Meka despite the fact that Mongo Meka is amongst the people who have plunged Ewawa into the economic doldrums therefore leading us to affirm that not all people from other provinces hate people from the First Province as demonstrated in the novel. Furthermore, Mula offers both food and a drink to a man who is from Ndotelle out of his likeness contrary to the people from Ndotelle who do not even care to give food to one of their relation from Ndotelle in Dande who has come to mourn for the death of Mongo Meka. Thus leading us to apply the cosmopolitan theory of Kwame Anthony as analysed by Mohammad Hossein Seifikar¹⁴ in reviewing the work of Kwame Anthony he observed that Kwame Anthony professed that the population should take interest in the lives of others, show kindness and generosity towards one another in the society. In addition, Mohammad Hossein Seifikar also commented that Kwame Anthony prescribed that people should practise eating, laughing and buying together. Relating this theory to our article, we will assert that, Mula is practising living together because Mongo Meka is not only from the ruling class but he has also contributed to the poor economic situation in Ewawa since he has embezzled morethan five hundred and fifty (550,000,000)million Frs. Mula offers him quality wine in France. The two Ewawains drink together furthermore, Mula offers both food and a drink to a man from Ndotelle who has come to Dande due to the death of Mongo Meka. Thus leading us to establish that Mula is promoting a harmonous society because he buys a drink for Mongo Meka and for himself and the two drink together. Moreover, Mula shows both generosity and kindness towards a man from the ruling class for as earlier mentioned there is animosity but people from the domonant tribe and those who are marginalised but Mula does not take the enmity into consideration for he offers but generosity to Ewawains.

We shall thus sum up our interpretation of the two quotations by establishing that, the author is calling on various individuals in Ewawa to take good care of people without taking into account their ethnic group as Mula has done both towards a have not and a person who has once been in power and who has fallen from grace to grass as seen in a man from Ndotelle in Dande and Mongo Meka in France thereby having a society void of tribalism and enmity.

¹⁴ Mohammad Hossein Schifikar. (ibid).

Additionally, by affirming that the author is using Mula as a character foil to the ruling class from both the First and the Second Provinces to stop thinking only of people from their tribes at the detriment of people from the eighth, ninth and tenth Provinces as presented in the novel. Finally, by stating that, the writer is indirectly calling on the ruling class to be nice to everyone in the community in order for Ewawa to be a tribaless one thus encouraging peaceful co-existence in the society.

Furthermore, on the efforts made by good Samaritans to encourage cohabitation in Ewawa, our seventh instance shall be demonstrated by quoting where the novelist says that Mula has looked for Sonia's admission in a Biberian university. Mula during the reception party organised in his honour by his friends Ndjock and Nchinda, Mula tells the friends that he has got admission for Sonia in his Biberian University and he shall therefore go with Sonia after his mission in Ewawa. (*The Dead*: 201).

From the words of Mula, we would suggest that the writer is portraying Mula as a kind person because he decides to look for admission for a friend in a foreign university without considering the tribe of Sonia though the author does not make mention of Sonia's tribe, what we have to drive home is that Ewawaians should imitate the good example of Mula thus leading us apply the cosmopolitan theory of Kwame Anthony as viewed by Mohammad Hossein Seifkar¹⁵ in reviewing the work of Kwame Anthony. He remarked that Kwame Anthony stated that citizens should take show kindness and generosity towards one another in the society. In additionally, Mohammad Hossein Seifkar equally remarked that Kwame Anthony advocated that people should practise eating, laughing, buying and attend parties together. Connecting this approach to our article, we will affirm that , both Mula and his mates are practising living together in Ewawa because the friends of Mula organise a party for him at their own expense where they eat and chat together thereby expressing solidarity and generosity while Mula on his part, shows both solidarity, kindness and generosity towards Sonia thus making us to allude to the biblical saying that 'love your neighbour as yourself'. Therefore, we will by establishing that, the novelist using fiction to advise other Ewawains to imitate the acts of Mula and the friends in order to promote peaceful co-existence in the society.

Still on the promotion of cohabitation Ewawa, our eighth example we will cite is the act of Mengue Brigitte's mother. The novelist informs us that she accommodates Lucia Ntang with her pregnancy for many months as the citation that follows attests:

¹⁵ Mohammad Hossein Schifkar. (ibid).

I wandered from compound to compound, from street to street waiting for dawn. It was a long, very long night. At last, dawn came and I had the opportunity to see a friend (Mengue) whose mother was a member of the legion of Mary. I told her about my predicament and asked her to talk to her mother to give me shelter for a few weeks while I looked for means and a place to take care of myself. Mengue Brigitte dutifully told her mother my request and she granted it. I told her my problem and how I came to find myself in the situation I was. She understood and pitied me for being a victim of ignorance. (The Day: 80).

To appraise the above quotation, we would assume that the author is portraying Mengue Brigitte's mother as a kind hearted woman who does not like tribalism since Mengue Brigitte's mother comes from the ruling tribe while Lucia Ntang comes from the class that is not in power. The author has used coincidence for it is through the struck of luck that Lucia Ntang meets with Mengue Brigitte. The use of this device is for plot advancement for had Mengue Brigitte not met with Lucia Ntang, perhaps the story could have taken a different turn. The coincidence is also out to portray that both Mengue Brigitte and the mother are hospitable, kind and understanding. This is in line with what Anke Graness¹⁶ who encourages hospitality and generosity in the society. Thus the fact that Lucia Ntang is housed together with her fatherless son for many months is a glaring example that Mengue Brigitte's mother is against clannism for the text tells us there is animosity between the ruling clans and the non-ruling clans as we have earlier mentioned. Therefore leading us to use the cosmopolitan approach of Johan Galtung¹⁷ who advocated for the non practice of ethnocentrism and marginalisation in the society. The relevance of this approach to our article is that, the novelist is out to appreciate the mother of Mengue Brigitte for accepting to accomodate Lucia Ntang despite the fact that Lucia Ntang is not from the same with her. She does not express enmity which exists between the dominant tribes and the marginalised tribes thus she is not tribalistic.

Still on the above analyses, we will also use the comsmopolitan theory, of Kwame Anthony. Hossein Seifikar¹⁸ in appraising the work of Kwame Anthony. He commented that Kwame Anthony mentioned that people should show kindness and generosity towards one another in the society. Linking this approach to our research, we will assert that the mother of Mengue Brigitte is promoting peaceful co-existence in Ewawa because she does not only

¹⁶ Anke Graness. "Unbuntu and the concept of Cosmopolitanism". *Human Affairs*. 28, 2018:395-405.

¹⁷ Johan Galtung. (ibid).

¹⁸ Mohammad Hossein Schifikar. (ibid).

accommodate Lucia Ntang with her unborn child, but she also show kindness and generosity towards her by feeding her until Lucia Ntang gives birth to her son. We shall then end our analyses on this point by stating that, the author is calling on other Ewawaians from the First and Second Provinces to behave like the mother of Mengue Brigitte so that Ewawa will become a non tribalistic nation thereby promoting living together in the country.

Still on the personal efforts people put in to promote living together in the country, our ninth proof will be quoted where the novelist tells us Jacqueline Diwona and Marie-Claire live together in the same house though they come from different tribes as the citation below attests:

One evening, she asked me to move room. She said she wanted me to share the same room with her – her late brother’s room. According to her, the room was too large, and she was afraid. I did not like the idea because I thought I would be made to sleep on a mat on the floor. Upon going into the room, since I had no choice, I carried a mattress. When she saw it and asked me its purpose and I told her, she said it was not necessary. She said she wanted me to share the same bed with her. (The Dead: 179).

To assess the quotation, we would think the writer is presenting Jacqueline Diwona as someone who is not in favour of working with house helps from her ethnic group for the text informs us that Jacqueline Diwona has maintained all the domestic servants that used to work with Antoinette Yvonne. Jacqueline Diwona does not minimise her house mates as seen in the words of Marie-Claire. Thus we see that Jacqueline Diwona loves Marie-Claire who is from another tribe because she asks Marie –Claire how bride price is paid in Marie-Claire’s tribe. We would then assume that, by not only inviting Marie-Claire to share the same room with her and to sleep on the same bed, but equally maintaining her as a maid though from a different tribe, shows that Jacqueline Diwona is against tribalism in Ewawa. Thus leading us to apply the cosmopolitan theory of For Kwame Anthony Appiah¹⁹ is a promoter of peaceful co-existence for he is against the practice of tribalism and marginalisation. The pertinence of this theory to our research is that, the novelist tells us that Jacqueline Diwona maintains all the formal servants of Antoinette Yvonne without taking into consideration that some of them like Marie –Claire who is from one of the marginalised tribes in Ewawa for the novel informs us that only persons from the ruling tribes are either recruited or employed in Ewawa. Thus by maintaining all the formal workers of the sister in law, the author is using Jacqueline Diwona

¹⁹ Kwame Anthony Appiah. (ibid).

as a character foil since other Ewawains from the ruling class recruit only persons from their clan. The use of the contrast is a means of the author is indirectly calling on other dinitaries from the dominant class to follow the example of Jacqueline Diwona in order to foster peaceful co-existence thereby reducing the level of not only unemployment, but equally the level of acrimony because the author informs us that the Ewawains from the 8th,9th and 10th provinces detests those from the ruling class in Ewawa because the ruling class employs or recruit those from their tribes.

We shall therefore end our commentaries on the above citation by asserting that, the author is calling on all Ewawaians to co-habit with Ewawains from different ethnic groups as seen in the case of Jacqueline Diwona and Marie-Claire so as to reduce inter-tribal hatred in the country which is disenable as exemplified in chapter four of our thesis thereby promoting peaceful co-existence in Ewawa.

Moreover, on living together, our last illustration will be by making reference to Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese. The novel informs us Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese gives his former class mate in the university Lucia Ntang a lift from the British Council to Obele. (*The Day*: 65-66). From the just mentioned sentences, we are of the opinion that the novelist is presenting Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese as an Ewawaian who does not practise bias by giving his class mate a lift from the British Council to Obele. For the novel tells us that Lucia Ntang is going back on foot and it is Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese who recognises Lucia Ntang and by hooting his car, Lucia Ntang's attention is drawn thereby leading to her entry into the car. Furthermore, the text even tells us that so many kilometres separate the British Council from Obele and that Lucia Ntang usually spends about six hundred (600) Frs. on taxi fare to and fro. Therefore leading us use the cosmopolitan theory of Kwame Anthony once more. Hossein Seifkar²⁰ in assessing the work of Kwame Anthony. He commented that Kwame Anthony mentioned that people should show kindness and generosity. Relating the approach to our work, we will assert that, the author is out to present Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese as an Ewawain who promotes peaceful cohabitation in the society because he transports Lucia Ntang from the British Council to Obele free of charge. We observe that there is no animosity between Lucia Ntang and Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese who comes from the ruling class whereas Lucia Ntang is from the marginalized tribe. We will then conclude our comments on Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese's generosity towards Lucia Ntang by affirming firstly, that, the author is saying that

not all people of the ruling class in Ewawa do practise clannism as illustrated in Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese. Secondly, by stating that the writer is presenting Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese as one of the people of good will who can salvage the Ewawaian society of ethnocentrism.

We will then sum up this section by ascertaining that, the novelists understudy is presenting the Passer-by Lady who carries a desperate person to hospital, Joseph who offers Lucia Ntang a job in a hotel, Maria's boyfriend who conducts a pregnancy test for Lucia Ntang free of charge, the Minister of Social Affairs who gives money to Lucia Ntang to take care of her fatherless son, Mula who offers both food and a drink to a man who is from Ndotelle and good wine to Mongo Meka in France, has sought for Sonia's admission in a Biberian university, Mengue Brigitte's mother who accommodates Lucia Ntang with her pregnancy for many months and Okinna Jean Pierre Marie-Therese who gives his former class mate in the university Lucia Ntang a lift from the British Council to Obele as good are all architects to prove people in Ewawa are living peacefully as presented in the novels under review.

Conclusion.

This study proposed cosmopolitan approach as the conceptual framework for reading post independent African literary novels conceived to analyse literary works that promote peaceful coexistence in the society. This study will thereby contribute to the promotion of peace in the community enormously it therefore, with its index, offers an alternative engagement paradigm in African literary criticism so that cosmopolitan theory can operate as a broad front for harmony to replace conflict in a continent where inter tribal conflicts are the order of the day. So by expressing solidarity, compassion mostly in times of difficulties to the needy based on the premise that we are one and not on tribal bases, accommodating and taking good care of persons from different tribes, employing persons without putting tribe first and by rendering services even to the poor without considering money first all go a long way to ease enmity between the ruling class and the govern thereby promoting living together in postcolonial Africa.

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